

Analysis of Opening Displacement of Transverse Cracks in Graphite-Epoxy Laminates for Permeation Modeling

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ABSTRACT

Composite laminates are widely used in many applications including cryogenic fuel tanks of reusable launch vehicles because of their high strength-to-weight ratio. During these applications, they are subjected to various complex thermo-mechanical loading, which initially leads to matrix cracking and then to delamination of plies. This type of damage can cause leakage in a fuel tank, making it permeable to the cryogenic fuel. Since the amount of leakage increases with crack opening displacement (COD), it is essential to study the effect of various factors like loading conditions, crack density and laminate orientation on COD. In this study, an analytical methodology based on shear lag analysis is developed to predict COD of a graphite-epoxy laminate subjected to different thermal and mechanical loading conditions and crack density. Finite element analysis was used to verify the mathematical model. Correlation between the model and FE analysis is generally good.

Keywords: shear lag analysis, crack opening displacement, transverse cracks, ply orientation, FEA

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are ideal for aerospace structural applications, such as reusable launch vehicles (RLV), where high strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios are required. However, it is feasible that when subjected to extreme temperature variations combined with dynamic structural loading, micro-cracks may evolve in the polymer matrix that could eventually make the tank wall permeable to the cryogenic fuel. These matrix cracks or micro-cracks are found extending through the thickness of an individual ply, typically oriented parallel to the fibers. The micro-cracks result mainly due to the mismatch in the Poisson's ratio and/or coefficient of thermal expansion between adjacent plies of different orientation.

Because of the potentially mission-critical implications of the permeation problem, many researchers have studied the permeation or leakage of cryogenic fuel through composite laminates by means of experiments [1-3]. McManus *et al* [1] found that permeability is strongly influenced by loading conditions, crack density and ply orientation. Kumazawa *et al* [2] developed leak analysis based on the opening displacements of matrix cracks and found that enlargement of crack opening displacement (COD) due to mechanical and thermal loads can cause increase in leak rate. Varna *et al* [4] predicted average COD based on shear-lag model and variational approach and found that the stiffness reduction in the uncracked layer influences the COD of the interior layer.

Since the amount of leakage through the laminate increases with evolving damage, it is essential to study the effect of various factors such as thermo-mechanical loading, crack density and uncracked ply orientation on COD in order to understand and quantify the influence of damage on cryogenic fuel permeation and/or leakage. In this study, an analytical methodology based on shear lag analysis [5, 6] is developed to predict COD in the 90° layers in a graphite-epoxy laminate (IM-6/3501-6)

subject to varying thermal and mechanical loading conditions and specified crack density. The shear lag model presented in this paper is based on the work performed by Maddocks and McManus [7]. The COD obtained using the shear lag model is verified using a finite element model. Similar analyses are repeated for different laminate lay-ups in order to study the influence of orientation of the uncracked (remaining) layer on COD in the cracked 90° layer.

SHEAR LAG ANALYSIS

In this section, a simple expression for COD is derived based on the shear lag analysis, applied at the vicinity of a crack. The difference between the axial displacements of cracked layer to the uncracked layer in the vicinity of a crack is employed to obtain the value of COD. A one dimensional shear lag model, as shown in Fig.1, is used to determine the stress and displacement fields in the vicinity of a crack in its local $x'y'z'$ coordinate system. The shear stress between cracked and uncracked layer is q . The thickness of the cracking layer and the rest of the laminate are a_c and a_r , respectively, and a_0 is the total laminate thickness. In this derivation, a subscript c denotes cracked plies, and a subscript r denotes uncracked (remaining) plies. The axial stress in each ply is denoted by σ , stiffness E , and coefficient of thermal expansion α .

Based on the shear lag analysis [7], the displacement of the cracking layer and the remaining layer, subjected to a thermal load ΔT , and an applied stress σ_a is found to be,

$$u_c = \frac{Ka_c x'}{2\zeta^2 E_c} \left[\frac{(a_r E_r + a_c E_c) \sigma_a + \alpha_r \Delta T}{a_r E_r E_0} \right] \left[1 - \frac{a_c}{2\zeta x'} \frac{\sinh(2\zeta x' / a_c)}{\cosh(2\zeta h / a_c)} \right] + \frac{\alpha_c \Delta T x'}{2\zeta^2 E_c} \left[2\zeta^2 E_c - Ka_c \left[1 - \frac{a_c}{2\zeta x'} \frac{\sinh(2\zeta x' / a_c)}{\cosh(2\zeta h / a_c)} \right] \right] \quad (1)$$

$$u_r = \frac{\sigma_a Ka_c^2 x'}{2\zeta^2 a_r E_r} \left[\frac{2a_0 \zeta^2}{Ka_c^2} - \frac{(a_r E_r + a_c E_c)}{a_r E_r E_0} \right] \left[1 - \frac{a_c}{2\zeta x'} \frac{\sinh(2\zeta x' / a_c)}{\cosh(2\zeta h / a_c)} \right] + \frac{\Delta T Ka_c^2 x'}{2\zeta^2 a_r E_r} \left[\frac{2\zeta^2 a_r E_r \alpha_r}{Ka_c^2} + (\alpha_c - \alpha_r) \right] \left[1 - \frac{a_c}{2\zeta x'} \frac{\sinh(2\zeta x' / a_c)}{\cosh(2\zeta h / a_c)} \right] \quad (2)$$

Where ζ is shear lag parameter, and K is effective shear stiffness.

Figure 1 Shear Lag Model Subjected to Thermal or Mechanical Load.

Assuming that a crack exists with crack spacing $2h$, then the opening displacement of a crack with a minimum crack density ($\rho=1/2h$) can be found as,

$$\text{COD} = u_c - u_r \quad (3)$$

Where the displacements u_c and u_r are calculated in the vicinity of a crack which is of interest. Due to symmetry of crack opening geometry, the COD in equation (3) represents half of the total crack opening. By changing the value of 'h' in Eqns. (1) and (2), the COD for a specified crack density can be found using the above expression.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

A two-dimensional finite element model as shown in Fig.2 was constructed to compute crack opening displacements occurring in laminates subjected to thermal or mechanical loads. Finite element analyses were performed using the commercial finite element software, IDEAS. The thickness a_0 of the uniform cross section of the model was assumed to be 0.036inch with each lamina 0.006inch thick. The length L of the model was 2 inch, and the crack density was increased by changing the crack spacing and increasing number of cracks in the model. In the current study, the crack density was varied from 1 to 25 cracks per inch. Due to symmetry of geometry and loading, only one half of the specimen was modeled as shown in Fig.2. Because the entire cross-section of the laminate parallel to XY plane deform in the same manner, a two-dimensional mesh consisting of 8-noded plane stress elements was used instead of a full 3-D finite element analysis. The COD along the crack face was obtained from the computed displacements at each node on the crack face. The average COD was computed by summing the COD at all nodes and dividing by total number of nodes on the crack face. Subsequently, The average COD value was used to compare with results obtained from the shear lag analysis. The finite element analyses were performed for both thermal and mechanical loading conditions with the crack density varying from 1 to 25. Similar analysis was performed for different laminate lay-ups, namely $[15/90_2]_s$, $[30/90_2]_s$, $[45/90_2]_s$, $[60/90_2]_s$, $[75/90_2]_s$, and $[90/90_2]_s$ in order to study the effect of uncracked layer's orientation on COD.

Figure 2. Finite element model of a laminate with transverse cracks.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In Fig. 3, the COD for $[0/90_2]_s$ lay-up is presented as a function of position across the 90-layer thickness for both thermal loading (Fig.3a) and mechanical loading (Fig.3b). It can be seen from the figure that the results from both the analyses are very close and the error was less than 1%. Fig. 4 shows the shear stress (Fig.4a) and longitudinal tensile stress (Fig.4b) distribution between two cracks of spacing 2h, for pure thermal loading. The shear stress in finite element analysis can be made to match the shear lag analysis by increasing the number of elements in the finite element mesh. Similar results were obtained for mechanical loading as well. The COD vs. crack density plot is shown in Fig. 5 for thermal (Fig.5a) and mechanical loading (Fig.5b). It can be seen that COD is fairly constant for low crack densities, but then starts to decrease rapidly when a critical crack density is exceeded, that is, when the spacing between adjacent cracks falls below a critical threshold.

Figure 3. Predicted COD of graphite-epoxy laminate for (a) thermal loading and (b) mechanical loading.

Figure 4. Shear stress and tensile stress distribution between two cracks of spacing 2h.

Crack opening volume (COV) vs. crack density plot is shown in Fig. 6 for both thermal loading (Fig.6a) and mechanical loading (Fig.6b). It can be seen that initially COV increases linearly with crack density, and then the rate of increase in COV begins to decline. Not surprisingly, this occurs at the point at which tensile stress at the cracking layer starts to decline rapidly because, as the crack density rises, the peak value of the longitudinal tensile stress which governs COD in the 90° layers starts to decrease. This behavior is clearly depicted in Fig.7 (a, b). From Figs.5-7, it is evident that the relationship between COD and crack density is fairly independent of the type of loading, i.e., thermal or mechanical.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. COD vs. crack density for (a) thermal loading and (b) mechanical loading.

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. COV vs. crack density for (a) thermal loading and (b) mechanical loading.

Figure 7. Tensile stress vs. crack density for (a) thermal loading and (b) mechanical loading.

Study on the effect of ply orientation on COD

The above analyses were performed for a symmetric, cross-ply laminate made of graphite-epoxy material IM-6/3501-6. In order to study the effect of the orientation of the uncracked or remaining layer on COD, similar analyses were performed for different laminate lay-ups, namely $[15/90_2]_s$, $[30/90_2]_s$, $[45/90_2]_s$, $[60/90_2]_s$, $[75/90_2]_s$, and $[90/90_2]_s$ for pure thermal and mechanical loadings, respectively. Fig. 8 shows the effect of orientation of uncracked layer on COD for pure thermal loading. It can be seen from Fig. 8 that COD reduces as the ply angle changes from 0 to 90 degree. This is due to the fact that the tensile stress at the vicinity of a crack drops to zero when ply angle changes from 0 to 90 degree as shown in Fig. 9, as the mismatch in CTE between adjacent plies disappears. Similar analyses were performed for pure mechanical loading and the results were shown in Fig. 10 and Fig. 11. For mechanical loading, COD increases as the uncracked ply angle changes from 0 to 90 degree. As the adjacent layer's stiffness reduces, the transverse ply carries more load, and hence more tensile stress, resulting in increased COD. A plot of the peak tensile stress vs. angle of uncracked layer for mechanical loading case is shown in Fig. 11.

Figure 8. COD vs. angle of uncracked layer for thermal loading.

Figure 9. Tensile stress vs. angle for thermal loading.

Figure 10. COD vs. angle of uncracked layer for mechanical loading.

Figure 11. Tensile stress vs. angle for mechanical loading.

For all of the above analyses very good agreement between shear lag analysis and finite element analysis was observed. It must be stated that this study was performed based on the assumption that the laminate consists of pre-existing cracks before the load is applied. Both the analyses were used to predict COD in transverse ply only, and can be modified to predict the COD's of adjacent layers as well. In order to clearly understand the behavior of permeation through composite laminates it is necessary to predict the COD for all layers. In future effort, an expression for permeation through composite laminates will be developed based on the results obtained from this study.

CONCLUSION

In the present paper, a simple expression for predicting opening displacement of a transverse crack was derived based on shear lag analysis and verified using finite element analysis. Using this expression, the COD can be calculated for any symmetric laminate lay-up for any given crack density and loading conditions. Good agreement was observed between the results obtained by SLA and FEA analyses. The study has lead to the following observations

- (a) As the crack density increases, COD tend to be constant and then starts to decrease rapidly when the crack density is very high. Similar behavior is observed for the tensile stress at the vicinity of a crack. This is due to the fact that, as the crack spacing decreases or, as crack density increases, the transverse ply loses its ability to carry much tensile load thus resulting in COD decrease. As the crack density increases, the crack opening volume increases linearly, but then the rate of increase starts to slow down. It is conjectured that for very high crack densities crack opening volume may reach saturation resulting in constant permeation through laminates irrespective of the increase in the number of cracks.
- (b) As the ply angle of the uncracked or remaining layer changes, the COD changes for both thermal and mechanical loading conditions. COD may decrease or increase depending on the loading conditions. It is clear from the analysis that COD is very sensitive to adjacent ply orientation and laminate lay-up plays a major role in either decreasing or increasing the permeability through a composite laminate. It should be noted that these observations were made for the graphite-epoxy (IM6/3501-6) laminate system and these conclusions may not transferable to other type of laminates.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported through a grant from NASA Langley Research Center, Hampton, VA. The authors are grateful to Dr. Thomas S. Gates for his valuable comments.

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